

Table—Uranyl 12-Molybdophosphate

%U	%P	$\frac{UO_2}{PMo_{12}O_{40}}$	$\frac{H_2O}{PMo_{12}O_{40}}$	pH	CH ⁺	$\frac{H^+}{PMo_{12}O_{40}}$
13.78	1.291	1.39	11.5	2.19	0.006253	1.36

To an aqueous solution of 12-Molybdophosphoric acid containing a drop of concentrated nitric acid, dry Uranyl Carbonate was added in the molar ratio 1:3 respectively. The suspension was then warmed over water bath and the clear solution was filtered out from the undissolved matter. It was concentrated over water bath and the concentrated liquor was then allowed to evaporate in a dish. Shining yellow crystals of Uranyl 12-Molybdophosphate appeared which were filtered washed with water and finally with alcohol. The compound was dried in sulphuric acid desiccator.

The salt is soluble in water and can be isolated from aqueous solution by crystallization. Uranyl 12-Molybdophosphate is an acid salt and contains 2.78 equivalents of the UO_2^{++} cation per mole of the anion. From the elemental analysis and hydron content measurement it appears that the salt may be represented as $(UO_2)_{1.39}H_{1.36}PMo_{12}O_{40}$, 11.5 H_2O .

Analysis :

Uranium and phosphorous of the compound were determined gravimetrically as U_3O_8 and alkalimetrically via ammonium molybdate respectively.

Hydron content of the salt has been determined by taking certain weight of the substance in definite volume of water and measuring the pH of the solution. From the pH value equivalent hydrogen-ion concentration per mole of the anion $PMo_{12}O_{40}$ was calculated. Water of crystallization of the salt was determined from the weight loss of the salt after keeping at 120° - 150° for 6 hr.

Result and Discussion :

Therefore apparent basicity = $1.39 \times 2 + 1.36 = 4.13$

Considering the basicity of 12 MPA as 3, the salt can be described as 'Normal salt' with very slight deficiency of base (2.8 instead of 3). pH determinations of the salt reveals the presence of approximately one equivalent of free H^+ per mole of 12 MPA. The presence of excess hydrogen ions the salt may be explained, following Ripan³, that 12 MPA has three strong hydrogens and that further hydrogen of the hydrated salt can ionize under certain conditions. The presence of these additional H^+ seems to provide an autostabilization for the salt since, true normal salt would have neutral or alkaline pH under which circumstances the $PMo_{12}O_{40}$ anion should be degraded to similar ions. Presumably in the presence of very low concentration of added mineral acid (one drop of conc. nitric acid), more than three hydrogen ions of the hydrated complex are able to dissociate. From all the above observations it appears that the salt is an acid salt and nonstoichiometric in character in keeping with the well known base exchange properties of the 12-Molybdophosphoric acid.

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Electron Transfer Reactions. II. Oxidation of Glyoximes.

A. M. TALATI and B. V. SHAH

Chemistry Department, M.S. University, Baroda.

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GLYOXIMES are known to be oxidised to furoxans by potassium ferricyanide^{1,2,3}, halogens^{1,2,4}, bleaching solutions^{1,5}, oxides of nitrogen⁶, etc. While studying the coordination chemistry of the oximino ligands, we observed that halogens form addition products with some metal glyoximates⁷ and that copper sulphate oxidises phenyl hydrazone of 2, 3-dioxobutyranilide 2-oxime.⁸ Following our studies on the oxidation of phenyl hydrazone oxime by various oxidants, we carried out the oxidation of 2, 3-dioxobutyranilide dioxime (I) to the furoxan derivative (II) with various oxidants. We find that (i) oxidation with peroxydisulphuric acid or chlorine is very vigorous and gummy mass is obtained, (ii) good yield is obtained with the oxidant like lead tetra-acetate and (iii) low yield is obtained with the oxidant like potassium ferricyanide. We observe that the yield is increasing in order,

These results indicate that lead tetra-acetate and potassium permanganate can be considered more suitable for the preparation of the furoxan by the oxidation of the glyoxime. Further, two-electron oxidants bring about oxidation to a greater extent than one-electron oxidants. Recently Burakevich, Lore and Volpp⁹ have shown that syn, anti and amphi isomeric forms of phenyl glyoxime yield the same phenyl furoxan derivative, and Brokenshire, Roberts and Ingold¹⁰ have shown that both isomeric iminoxy radicals (a) $>C=N-O$ and (b) $>C=N \rightarrow O$ are obtained regardless of which of the isomeric forms is oxidised. Hence the mechanism of oxidation reaction can be represented as follows :

1. For one electron oxidants :

2. For two electron oxidants :

Since better yields are obtained with two electron oxidants, oxidation leading to the formation of biradical in a single step is considered more favoured than the oxidation leading to the formation of biradical in steps. It may be attributed largely to the nature (case of oxidation) of the two-oximino groups.

Experimental :

Preparation of 2, 3-dioxobutyranilide 2-oxime and 2, 3-dioxobutyranilide dioxime :

These were prepared by the method of Dave and Talati¹¹.

Oxidation with potassium permanganate :

1g. potassium permanganate in 50ml water was added in small quantities at a time over a period of 1 hr to 0.5 g (I) in 3 ml 10% sodium hydroxide solution. The mixture was kept for 3 hr more at room temperature and filtered. The residue was extracted with ether and the extract was evaporated to dryness. The product was recrystallised from dilute acetic acid as white crystals melting at 149° (m. p. (lit) : 149°-51°) Yield : 55-60%.

Oxidation with potassium ferricyanide :

0.8 g. potassium ferricyanide in 5 ml water was added dropwise to 0.5 g. (I) in 2 ml 10% sodium hydroxide solution. The mixture was left at room temperature for 1/2 hr and filtered. The product was recrystallised from dilute acetic acid as white crystals melting at 149°. Yield : 15-20%

Oxidation with lead dioxide :

Excess of lead dioxide was added gradually over a period of 1 hr, to the suspension of 0.5 g (I) in 20 ml 25% acetic acid, with stirring. The mixture was stirred for 3 hr more and filtered. The residue was extracted with ether and the extract was evaporated to dryness. The product was recrystallised from dilute acetic acid (using charcoal) as white crystals melting at 149°. Yield : 35-40%.

Oxidation with iron (III) chloride :

2 g. iron (III) chloride in 45 ml water and 1 g. (I) in 15 ml alcohol were mixed and few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid were added to it dropwise with stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 1 hr and filtered

hot. The product separated out on cooling the filtrate, It was filtered and recrystallised from dilute acetic acid, as white crystals melting at 149°. Yield : 35-40%.

Oxidation with lead tetra-acetate :

Lead tetra-acetate was prepared as suggested in "Preparation of organic intermediates"¹²

2 spoons of freshly prepared lead tetra-acetate were added in small quantities at a time over a period of 30 min, to the rapidly stirred solution of 1 g. (I) in 20 ml acetic acid. The mixture was stirred for 30 min more and filtered. The mixture was poured into water. The product was filtered and recrystallised from dilute acetic acid as white crystals melting at 149°. Yield : 60-65%.

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